

“Bring me sunshine, bring me (physical) strength”: The case of dementia. Designing and implementing a virtual reality system for physical training during the COVID-19 pandemic

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ABSTRACT

People living with Dementia (PwD) are amongst the most vulnerable populations in society, often depending on caregivers for their quality of life (QoL). Emerging research confirms the need for technological solutions to support non-pharmacological interventions that can enhance the QoL of PwD. This paper posits that Virtual Reality (VR) is a useful technology for boosting the physical training of PwD. In a study with PwD, we compared the conventional physical training PwD receive at a nursing home, against Semi Immersive VR (SIVR) and Fully Immersive VR (FIVR) training paradigms. We recorded the emotional behaviour, task-specific metrics, and level of independence of PwD during the training. The presence and usability of the system by both medical staff and PwD was also assessed. Results indicated that FIVR can improve the training of PwD leading to more accurate execution of the exercises while preventing external distractions. Beyond the findings, this article discusses the opportunities, challenges, along with the feasibility and acceptability of VR, to facilitate physical training for PwD who reside in restricted health care environments.

1. Introduction

Dementia includes a range of progressive symptoms linked to disorders of the brain, which result in impairments of cognitive and motor functions (Rose et al., 2018). According to WHO an estimated 55 million people are living with dementia worldwide (WHO, 2021). As the global population is increasingly ageing, it is expected that this number will increase further. In particular, within the next thirty years, this number is expected to rise to about 139 million people (WHO, 2021). This expected growth makes imperative the need for better hospitalization and increased support towards PwD (Verbeek et al., 2010) who exhibit impairments in cognitive and motor functions, while also suffering from other co-existing symptoms, such as depression, apathy, lack of motivation, and loss of interest in oneself and others (Brett and Murnion, 2015; Kitching, 2015; Muliya and Varghese, 2010). These symptoms become most obvious during the late stages of the disease with PwD having difficulty performing basic functions and experiencing more drastic cognitive and behavioural changes.

With the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare systems

implemented unprecedented restrictions to control and reduce the transmission of the disease (Sohrabi et al., 2020). In healthcare clinics and nursing homes, restrictions were applied to outpatient visits (Bonavita et al., 2020) to reduce the risk of the contagion of the disease. In particular, visits to inpatients from family members and friends were banned (Cipriani and Di Fiorino, 2020; US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020). These restrictions impacted negatively the physical and mental health of patients, and especially the older patients who are most vulnerable to the COVID-19 disease (Cipriani and Di Fiorino, 2020).

Older patients have a higher risk of morbidity and death when infected with COVID-19 because of their advanced age and frequent medical comorbidities. Dementia is considered one of the most common medical comorbidities (11.9%) amongst COVID-19 fatalities (Cipriani and Di Fiorino, 2020; Brown et al., 2020) because PwD are more likely to suffer from cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and pneumonia, compared to individuals of the same age without dementia (Bauer et al., 2014). These conditions are associated with poorer outcomes including death, in individuals with COVID-19 (Zhou et al., 2020). Consequently, PwD

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are advised to adhere to social distancing, leading to social isolation that may increase the risk of cognitive and physical decline (Cuffaro et al., 2020; Hawton et al., 2011; Kelly et al., 2017; Kuiper et al., 2015; Schrempft et al., 2019).

Alzheimer Europe recommended that PwD engage in leisure activities that will keep them mentally and physically active, even when social distancing measures are in place (Alzheimer Europe, 2020). Similarly, the WHO encouraged PwD living at home or in healthcare facilities to engage constantly in regular physical activity (WHO, 2015). Alzheimer's Disease International suggested that substantial support for PwD and their carers is needed worldwide (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2020).

In the age of information and communications technology, technological interventions can ease social distancing restrictions and at the same time improve the physical and cognitive level of PwD. This paper aims to describe the process of designing a Virtual Reality (VR) system for the physical training of PwD. Results are presented from the evaluation of its effectiveness in training PwD compared to the conventional routine. Specifically, the goals of the current study are (1) to assess whether VR can be effective in the physical training of PwD, especially at the latter stages of the disease, and (2) to explore the factors under which VR can enhance the QoL for PwD who reside in mental health units.

2. Related work

2.1. Exercise and PwD

One promising way to improve the mental and physical health of PwD is through exercise. Indeed, many studies highlight that PwD who exercise regularly have improved motor functions, stronger upper and lower bodies, and better walking balance compared to those who do not engage in any type of physical activity (Santana-Sosa et al., 2018). Also, many studies report a negative relationship between cognitive decline and exercise, suggesting that cognitive decline could be delayed by systematic physical activity (Brown et al., 2015; Vreugdenhil et al., 2012). Thus, it could be that regular physical activity can boost cognitive function, preventing the further development of neurological conditions and cognitive decline (Cheng et al., 2014; Loprinzi et al., 2013).

Even though the benefits of exercise are well documented, research also demonstrates that PwD may be reluctant to take part in physical training. Barriers may arise from mental and physical impairments that limit or prevent patient engagement in exercise. In particular, as the disease progresses, PwD encounter difficulties with orientation in space, which affects their understanding of the requirements of an exercise (Savva et al., 2009). Attention, memory and language processing difficulties also interfere with their understanding (Yu, and Kolanowski, 2009). In addition, PwD generally exhibit increased apathy and loss of motivation and interest in oneself and others (Clarke et al., 2008; Crombie et al., 2004; Kitching, 2015; Muliya and Varghese, 2010), which contributes to their reluctance to engage in any form of physical activity. As a result, most PwD find physical training to be boring and tedious (Nyman, 2011; Suttanon et al., 2012).

To overcome these barriers and to improve engagement in regular exercise and physical activity in PwD, several types of exergaming have been developed, showing some early promising results. For example, a study showed that the memory of dementia patients is improved by bowling on Nintendo Wii regularly (Fenney and Lee, 2010). In addition, another study revealed that cognition was improved by performing upper and lower limbs exergaming tasks, such as catching virtual coins or playing the drums, in front of a screen with customized controllers (Yamaguchi et al., 2011). Improvements in cognition, gait, and balance in PwD are also reported by a study that compared virtual to normal walking tasks (Padala et al., 2012). Specifically, results indicated improved gait and balance for people who exercised virtually using the Wii Fit console compared to a real-world walking program; this

improvement was attributed to the high levels of presence associated with the virtual exposure.

2.2. VR and PwD

VR allows users to experience a computer-simulated reality with visual, auditory, tactile, and/or olfactory cues (Li et al., 2011). Based on the level of immersion a VR system offers, it can be classified into the following three types (Ma and Zheng, 2011). A Non-Immersive VR system is a desktop computer-based 3D graphical system that allows users to navigate a virtual environment using a keyboard, mouse, and computer screen. A Semi Immersive (SIVR) system, projects graphical content on one or more large screens, and it may offer some form of gesture recognition for natural interaction (i.e., projected VR, CAVE, etc.). Finally, a Fully Immersive (FIVR) system uses a head-mounted display (HMD) to present content to users. Thus, in FIVR vision is completely enveloped, creating a sense of total immersion.

Based on a study that confirmed the abilities of PwD to experience presence (Flynn et al., 2003), several studies used VR to improve the QoL for this group. Most of the research with VR and dementia has focused on the improvement of specific abilities that decline over the course of the disease. These abilities typically relate to general cognition (Cheng et al., 2014; Loprinzi et al., 2013; Littbrand et al., 2011; Pitkälä et al., 2013; Potter et al., 2011), memory (Optale et al., 2010), spatial navigation (Cushman et al., 2008; Zakzanis et al., 2009), and executive functions such as planning activities (Manera et al., 2015), attention (Doniger et al., 2018; Manera et al., 2016), and motor control (Matsangidou et al., 2020).

In general, and within the context of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), research has mostly focused on the specific needs that PwD need to address. Past studies have examined what elements a VR-based system should incorporate, with the main conclusion that special care should be placed in creating personalized experiences that consider the preferences and skill level of each user (Eisapour et al., a, b; Hodge et al., 2018; Rose et al., 2019; Siriaraya, and Ang, 2014; Tabbaa et al., 2019).

More recently, some works have explored the opportunities and challenges of designing a VR system for PwD. In one such work (Eisapour et al., 2020), a methodology is proposed for the participatory design of a VR system for the physical activity of PwD. Five different games were designed for upper body exercises, in two different VR-based environments, and were then compared to traditional therapist-guided exercise training. The study showed encouraging results, with the VR-based sessions, having comparable results to the traditional approach. In another work, the design process for an immersive exergame for PwD is presented (Karaosmanoglu et al., 2021). PwD were tasked with taking photographs of landmarks in a virtual representation of their city of residence. The results, again, showed positive outcomes in areas like enjoyment, social interaction, usability, etc. Both of the above studies, however, had a limited number of participants, with five and eleven PwD participating, with mostly mild conditions of dementia.

The present study describes the design and development of a VR-based physical training system for PwD who reside in a confined mental health unit. Unlike prior works, and overcoming a limitation of the current literature, the system is evaluated with a larger population, ranging from moderate to even severe cases of dementia. To accomplish this a comparison of a SIVR and a FIVR system against the conventional routine training of PwD is performed, with 20 PwD with mild to severe dementia. The decision, unlike previous works, to evaluate both SIVR and FIVR systems was made based on the teams' experience, working with the population, where some PwD were hesitant putting on an HMD. The comparison between the two systems, which has not been performed before with this population, has the potential to guide future development of VR systems, and ensure the usability of such systems by PwD across different severities of the syndrome. The evaluation included an analysis of the emotional behaviour of PwD, their training

performance, and their level of independence while performing the training. Therefore, the current study tries to assess whether VR can be an effective tool for supporting physical training and enhancing the QoL for PwD who reside in a confined mental health unit during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. Co-Design process for VR system for PwD

The research and development team consisted of 53 medical and paramedical staff with experience in working with PwD and 5 HCI in healthcare experts. More specifically, the design process involved eight psychologists (with specializations in clinical ($n = 3$), cognitive ($n = 1$), developmental/social ($n = 1$), and general psychology ($n = 3$)), four physiotherapists, two occupational, two speech therapists, and four music/art therapists, three social workers, two physical trainers, twenty-eight PwD caregivers, and five HCI in healthcare experts (with specializations in: computer science ($n = 4$), and digital health ($n = 1$)). The team was thus comprised of experts who were able to cover a wide range of related areas of the development of this program (clinical content, system usability and technical development).

Over a year, a co-design process was followed, using focus groups, interviews, and pilot evaluations to design and develop the VR system (Fig. 1). The design of the system evolved through 7 milestones, before its final deployment. Pilot testing was carried out with a total of 50 end-users across the development process. This included both healthcare experts, as well as people with mild to severe dementia (range = 4 to 7 of the Global Deterioration Scale rating (GDS; Lawton et al., 1999).

3.1. Requirements specification

The first phase of the co-design process focused on the requirements specification for the system.

3.1.1. Literature review & barriers identification

Initially, a systematic literature review on VR and neurological conditions was performed. The review, despite the limited number of related studies showcased VR as a promising solution to enhance the physical training of PwD. The results of the review were then presented by a group of HCI researchers to a team of healthcare experts, with a focus on the technological possibilities of VR. The medical experts demonstrated the regular physical training of PwD, and a focus group ensued discussing mental and physical barriers that limit or prevent PwD engagement with exercise.

Key barriers that were identified include: (1) difficulties in attention, loss of memory and language processing (i.e., the therapist had to perform the exercise continuously in front of the PwD); (2) loss of

motivation (i.e., the training is perceived as long and boring); (3) difficulties and confusion in understanding/processing the exercise.

3.1.2. Exercise selection & requirements specification

The next step in the process involved the requirements specification. The healthcare experts selected two exercises that could be adapted in a VR-based system. These were the overhead arm raise and seated cable row. The HCI experts formalized the system requirements and created a storyboard on how they envisioned the VR system. This included UI elements, virtual environment ideas, embodiment elements, interaction techniques, etc. A second workshop was then held to discuss the requirements of the system. The HCI experts presented possible virtual environments that were then rated by the healthcare experts, selecting a virtual environment of a forest as the most appropriate. In addition, it was decided relating to the embodiment, to only present the hands of the PwD in the virtual environment and not a full avatar. This was decided as it was deemed to be less confusing for PwD, according to the healthcare experts, while also conveying all the necessary information for them to perform the exercises.

3.2. Prototype design & evaluation

Following the requirements specification phase, an iterative process of prototype design and evaluation was adopted. This was based on a combination of the Rapid Iterative Testing and Evaluation (RITE) methodology (Medlock et al., 2002) and within-subjects study design for specific features.

3.2.1. Interaction design

Based on the selected exercises and the specified requirements, a prototype was developed to evaluate how the interaction with the system should be performed. Two different options were designed, one using just touch, where virtual objects would be triggered by touching them with the controller, and one using a grab mechanism, where a button on the controller was used to trigger a virtual object once it's touched. Both options were tested using a seated cable row exercise, and visual and auditory feedback were included to illustrate a successful interaction. The interaction options were then evaluated through a pilot testing of the related prototypes. Ten PwD (five male, and five female), three physiotherapists, two psychologists and a developer participated in the session. The results suggested that PwD were able to complete the exercise tasks successfully, and with less assistance from the physiotherapist when simple interactions were assigned to the VR system (first interactivity option using just touch). Therefore, any use of buttons was avoided.

Fig. 1. Co-Design Process.

3.2.2. Scenario design

With the interaction method selected, gamified versions of the two exercises were designed. For the purposes of the prototype, an outdoor field environment was selected, and PwD were placed in the middle standing on a wooden platform. For the overhead arm raise exercise, a rope, which included 10 knots at equal distances, dropped down to the platform. PwD had to climb up the vertical rope by raising each hand alternately. With each alternation they would grab the next knot on the rope all the way to the top on an overhead platform. For the seated cable row, a similar task was presented this time with a horizontal rope they had to pull. As in the previous exercise, the rope included 10 knots at fixed distances. To pull the rope PwD had to perform a rowing motion with their hands. Thus a pilot testing was carried out to identify the feasibility and usability of the system, with ten PwD (five male, and five female), three physiotherapists, two psychologists and a developer. PwD were able to complete the exercise tasks successfully, but issues were detected with: (1) visual limitations of the virtual environment; (2) lack of engagement from PwD with the virtual environment; (3) difficulty of some PwD completing and engaging with certain exercises, due to their physical abilities that did not allow them to reach the predefined targets in the virtual environment; (4) three of the PwD were experiencing high rates of anxiety related to the VR device, resulting in the patient being unable to engage with the virtual environment; (5) the therapist had trouble following what PwD were experiencing in VR.

To resolve the various issues identified from the pilot testing several steps were taken. The physiotherapists requested for the seated cable row exercise to be replaced by a side arm raise exercise, while the overhead arm raise was changed to an overhead press so it can be performed simultaneously by both hands. It was also decided to add a calibration phase before the start of each exercise to measure the range of motion (ROM) of PwD and adapt the targets based on the measured range. This would reduce any frustrations and enable PwD to better perform the exercise tasks according to their physical abilities. The calibration was performed with the participant performing a correct repetition of the exercise, as judged and guided by the therapist. Once the correct repetition was performed, both the starting and ending positions for the exercise, as well as the movement trajectory during the exercise, were recorded and used as a template for the execution of the remaining repetitions.

3.3. Environment design

To explore the lack of engagement from PwD, a focus-group discussion was carried out for the selection of a virtual environment with the active participation of PwD. Participants in the study included eighteen PwD (eight male, and ten female) and fifty-one medical and paramedical personnel experienced with PwD (three clinical psychotherapists, three psychologists, four physiotherapists, two occupational therapists, two speech therapists, four music/art therapists, three social workers, two physical trainers, and twenty-eight caregivers). The discussion yielded five different categories of environments that could be

used. The categories were: nature, hobbies and sports, home, travel, and patient-familiar content.

Based on the selected categories, the development team found various freely and commercially available environments, that could fulfil the specified requirements. Next, a second focus group took place to select the final environment to be used for the scenario. The focus group included sixteen PwD and eight medical and paramedical staff (with specializations in psychology ($n = 2$), physical training ($n = 2$), caregivers ($n = 2$), physiotherapist ($n = 1$), and social worker ($n = 1$)). Images of the identified environments were presented and after a discussion, all participants voted for their preferred environment. The selected environment was an outdoor landscape that included a river and trees (Fig. 2). The results showed that the environment was rated as pleasant by participants and improved their mood. The study also found that the environment elicited reminiscence about the patients' past life experiences This was due to elements of the environment, having similarities to areas in the home country of the participants. These included a brick-build bridge, the terrain including the river, the cable lines, etc.

To investigate the feelings of anxiety from some of the PwD, it was decided to use a VR HMD integrated with an eye-tracking sensor. The technology allowed the analysis of the behaviour and gaze patterns of PwD, thus providing the opportunity to gain a better understanding of what PwD were experiencing. The tracked gaze of the PwD was decided to be displayed as a red line in the direction where PwD were looking (see Fig. 3). This information was only visible on the therapists' screen, and not within the HMD, as that could had confused PwD. This way the therapist provided better guidance accordingly.

To further support the therapists, it was decided to add an overlay on the therapists' screen, only visible to the therapist, providing additional patient-related information. These would include a count of the number of repetitions of each hand, as well as a representation of an avatar mirroring the in-game movements of PwD, along with the targets needed to touch. The need for the screen was created from instances where PwD would look around the environment, not focusing on the task at hand. In such cases, the observance of the mirrored avatar can provide useful feedback to better guide PwD on what they need to achieve and where to look. The repetition count could also provide a live tracker of the accuracy of the repetitions the participants are doing, as no other visual tracker was included in the scenario.

3.4. Simplification & revisions

A simplified gamified experience was designed to alleviate any disorientation or confusion the tasks during the previous prototype might be causing. The designed task, which was common for both exercises, required PwD to collect spheres that appeared in the environment based on their ROM. Using the starting and ending positions of the movement that were recorded through the calibration phase introduced earlier in Section 3.2.2, simple red sphere appeared in front of PwD as shown in Fig. 2. Upon being touched, the spheres turned green, before another sphere appeared at the next target position. The collection of the

Fig. 2. Representation of the virtual content which was used as the backdrop at the SIVR and FIVR sessions.

Fig. 3. To the left: Representation of the physiotherapist display enhanced with a human-stick figure to represent the PwD movement in an in-game panel, along with representations of the targets (red spheres). To the right: Representation of the PwD eye-gaze (red line) to represent what the PwD is looking at.

spheres, and thus the correct execution of the exercises, was rewarded with audio feedback, and increase in the score for the exercise. The sphere targets were exaggerated to be more visible and moved within the frontal field of view of the PwD so that the patients could appropriately interact with the system.

The system with the interaction changes, and the new virtual environment, was evaluated by seven PwD (two male, and five female), two physiotherapists, an HCI expert, and a developer. Positive feedback was received from both medical staff and PwD. Eye-tracking analysis showed that the reason for the irrelevant responses of the anxious patients to the visual stimulus was because they were closing their eyes once the headset was placed on their heads. As such appropriate guidance was provided to better familiarize them with the HMD. The VR eye-tracking device was agreed to be used during all training sessions to gather additional data related to the PwD behaviour and to provide real-time feedback to the therapist. Moreover, the use of the abstract figure to represent the PwD moves, along with representations of the targets was useful for the therapists to better track the progress of PwD, and it was further suggested to incorporate this into the virtual environment to inform the patient as well.

3.5. Polishing & deployment

The revised systems' evaluation showcased the feasibility of the designed system, and thus it was decided once some final adjustments were made to carry out a more extensive evaluation of the final polished prototype. The details of this final version of the system and its evaluation are described in the following sections. Finally, the system was deployed into a dementia restricted hospital environment and is currently being used in sessions run with PwD daily to assess longer-term effects of the use of the system.

4. The VR system

To evaluate the final version of the system, two different versions were tested, one using FIVR, and one using SIVR. The decision to perform the study with both a FIVR and SIVR stemmed from experiences during the development of the system, where some PwD felt uncomfortable wearing the HMD. Such occurrences have also been documented before in literature as well (Tabbaa et al., 2019; Matsangidou et al., 2020). The study of both systems could showcase the feasibility of the use of either of the two VR systems, so they can be both used based on what the PwD are more comfortable with. A description of each of the two systems follows.

4.1. FIVR

The system used in the study was developed using the Unity3D www.unity3d.com game engine. The 3D models for the virtual environment were acquired from the Unity Asset Store, with appropriate adjustments and additions made using Autodesk Maya. www.autodesk.com/products/maya/ For VR the VIVE Pro-Eye VR www.vive.com/eu/product/vive-pro-eye headset was used. Head position and orientation were captured by the HMD, while four Vive Trackers www.vive.com/eu/vive-tracker/ were attached to the wrists and above the elbow of each arm of the participant to capture arm movements (see Fig. 4 for the system setup).

The virtual environment presented a landscape with grass, hills, trees, a brick bridge, and a large lake, etc. (Fig. 5). The sky included flocks of birds and the grass and tree leaves moved along the wind. An audio mix with nature sounds, including birds, and sounds of the wind was playing in the background. Through the design process, it was shown that elements within the environment, resembled ones typical in the countryside in the participants' home country. PwD, during the experience were placed along the riverside facing the lake, while an avatar facing them, represented the trainer, providing in-game instructions. To execute the exercises, targets were displayed within the environment based on each exercise as simple red spheres that the participant had to touch. Once touched, the spheres would turn green

Fig. 4. The system setup with the VIVE Pro-Eye VR HMD and four Vive Trackers.

Fig. 5. PwD performing the overhead press exercise, via the SIVR version of the system.

and a pleasant sound would play with each successful attempt. The process would repeat based on the required number of repetitions for the exercise. The participants' hand movements, as captured by VIVE trackers were mapped to gloves shown in the virtual environment, as shown in Fig. 2.

The VR content that was seen by the PwD, was also streamed to a large monitor, mirroring the participant's real-time interactions so that the therapist can follow what the participants were experiencing. The monitor was within the line of sight of the therapist, and thus easy to follow while they were assisting the PwD. Also, to assist the therapist, an overlay only visible to the therapist and not displayed in the HMD, with additional information was visible at the side of the screen (see Fig. 3). This included data like the patient information, the current count of repetitions per arm, and an avatar representing the participants along with the targets they need to touch. The therapists' screen also included eye-tracking data captured by the integrated eye-tracking sensor within the HMD. This offered the ability to the therapist to observe the PwD and guide them accordingly. Again, the eye-tracking data were not visible to the participant but allowed the physiotherapist and the researchers to focus on what PwD were looking at.

4.2. SIVR

The SIVR system was based on the FIVR system with some minor changes. For example, while the movements of PwD were still captured using the VIVE Trackers, no HMD was used. Instead, the content, as seen through the HMD in the FIVR condition, was streamed from a laptop to a 55-inch TV that was located at 2.5 m from the patient at eye level (see Fig. 5 for the actual experimental set-up). Since the HMD was not used, the viewpoint within the virtual world was static (i.e., there was no ability to rotate the camera and view a different area of the virtual environment). Additional information displayed only to the therapist in the FIVR condition (i.e., the overlay with the patient information, and the eye-tracking data) were instead only displayed on a laptop screen, as to not be visible to the PwD.

5. Methods

The system was evaluated at a National Health in-patient and out-patient Alzheimer's and Dementia's disease hospital.

5.1. Ethics

Patients diagnosed with dementia were recruited from a National Health in-patient and out-patient Alzheimer's and Dementia's disease

hospital. Ethical approval was obtained from the National Bioethics Committee (reference is hidden for blind review). All participants signed a consent form before the study. The patient's capacity to consent to participate was established with a capacity assessment undertaken by a registered professional not part of the study. In cases where it was deemed that a patient did not have the capacity to consent on their own, a representative was contacted in the form of a friend, family member, or independent advocate and asked to provide consent in the form of best interest decision. Participants who lacked the capacity to consent were removed from the study if their representative withdrew from the study.

5.2. Participants

A total of 60 PwD were screened for inclusion. A history of severe motion sickness or vertigo that typically poses a risk of nausea and impending anxiety was set as an exclusion criterion. Additional exclusion criteria used during recruitment were the presence of aggression and/or overfamiliar behaviour; however, behaviour that challenges was acceptable because of the nature of the dementia disease. Patients confined to bed were also excluded from the study.

Applying these exclusion criteria yielded the 29 participants described above as eligible to participate. Only five PwD was deemed to have the capacity to consent to their participation, for the rest a consultee was contacted to consider consent to participate on their behalf. As a result, 20 PwD consented and nine declined. Therefore, the final sample of PwD included in the study was 20.

Twenty people with mild to severe dementia (seven male, and thirteen female), aged between 50 and 94 years ($M = 77.85$, $SD = 11.35$), participated in this study. Their average number of years living with dementia was 3.45 years ($SD = 3.12$) and ranged between 1 and 15 years. The mean Global Deterioration Scale rating (GDS; Lawton et al., 1999) was 5.6 ($SD = 1.43$), corresponding to "moderately-severe cognitive decline" (range = 2 to 7: "mild to severe dementia"). The primary diagnoses of the participants included dementia in Alzheimer's disease ($n = 20$). Secondary diagnoses amongst participants included major depressive disorder with recurrent depressive episodes ($n = 14$) and clinical anxiety ($n = 15$), and paranoid schizophrenia ($n = 2$).

5.3. Exercises

All training activities involved upper body movements that can be performed actively from a seated position, eliminating thus the risk of falling. In each training, participants were instructed to perform two seated exercises for 10 repetitions each. The selected exercises were: (a)

Overhead Press and (b) Side Arm Raise (Fig. 6). To perform the Overhead Press exercise, the participant must repetitively position each arm at shoulder height, then raise both arms above the head and keep them there for a couple of seconds before returning them to shoulder height. To perform the Side Arm Raise, the participant must lift repetitively both arms up and out to each side of the core by keeping the arms almost completely straight at shoulder height, forming a "T" shape. Then, the participant must lower the arms and bring them back to the sides. The Side Arm Raise is easier to carry out than the Overhead Press. It is generally performed faster and leads to lower pain and exhaustion.

5.4. Instruments

During each session, various metrics, both qualitative and quantitative, were collected.

5.4.1. Task-related metrics

Various task performance-related metrics were collected as follows:

Task Independence: the number of times (out of 10) the participant requested assistance from the physiotherapist to perform the exercise. Thus, the more times assistance was requested, the lower the score was on this measure.

Accuracy: assessed how many times (out of 10) the participant reached the targets correctly.

Duration. The duration of each exercise was measured in seconds from the time the participant started the first attempt and ended when the participant completed the 10th attempt to reach a target.

Movement. Movement data were captured by the system and analysed to identify patterns for each exercise over the progression of each task. The PwD performed a correct repetition of each exercise before the start of the 10 repetitions, which was used for calibration purposes. The accuracy of this first repetition was assessed by the physiotherapist assisting the PwD to ensure the proper execution of the exercise. This repetition was then used as a baseline to assess the quality of the movement during each repetition. A Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm (Salvador and Chan, 2007) was used to compare the similarity of each repetition to the baseline. A score from 0 to 1, with 1 being an exact match, was assigned to each repetition by the system.

Eye-tracking. Gaze data were collected from the eye-tracking sensor of the headset and were used to determine the focus of attention of PwD during the FIVR experience. Three different areas of interest were specified (i.e., targets, mirrored avatar representation, and virtual hands). For each area, various metrics were computed like the dwell time, which indicates the total time the participant was looking at the area, the fixation time, which is a consecutive period of at least 50 ms when the participant was fixated somewhere within the area, the number of visits, describing how many times the participant looked at the target, and average time per visit, which is how long the participant was looking at the area during each visit.

Except for task independence, which was measured by the therapist assisting the PwD, the rest of the task performance metrics were

automatically logged by the system.

5.4.2. Questionnaire data

Additional data were collected by an HCI Researcher with a background in Psychology and experience in working with PwD through a series of questionnaires. To validate those questions were well-understood by PwD during the administration of the questionnaires, appropriate adjustments were made to simplify the questions. The simplifications were made after discussing with experts in the field. Questions were also communicated according to the cognitive condition of PwD at the time, while at the same time the healthcare staff that was with the participant, could assess their state of mind and cohesion.

Observed Emotion Rating Scale (OERS) (Lawton et al., 1999). OERS was used to assess the patients' mood during the experimental session and between the different conditions. The OERS is an observational tool that was designed for use specifically in health care settings. It measures the time spent expressing five affect types, 2 positive ones (pleasure and general alertness) and 3 negative ones (anger, fear/anxiety, sadness). Each emotion is rated by selecting for how long, from a predefined set of durations, the emotion was observed. The scale was held by the researcher for the duration of the session.

Visual analogue Scale (VAS) (Crichton, 2001). VAS was used to obtain from patients a self-assessment of their emotions towards each condition. The patients were asked to point to the emoji (0 = happy and 5 = sad) that matched their emotional state before and after each condition.

Slater-Usoh-Steed Questionnaire (VRSQ) (Usoh et al., 2000). A simplified version of the VRSQ assessed the level of presence and immersion for the SIVR and FIVR conditions on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = being somewhere else and 7 = being in the virtual environment). The simplification of the questionnaire was performed by discussing with experts in the field how to convey each question in a way it can be easily understood by PwD.

System Usability Scale (SUS) (Brooke, 1986). A simplified version of the SUS assessed usability for the SIVR and FIVR conditions on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree). Again, the simplification of the questionnaire was performed with the assistance of experts in the field.

The Single Ease Question (SEQ) (Tedesco and Tullis, 2006). SEQ assessed the level of difficulty for the SIVR and FIVR training sessions on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = very difficult and 7 = very easy).

5.5. Procedure

The experiment required that each participant attends a session where three different conditions were tested: (a) Conventional/Control, (b) SIVR (Section 4.2), and (c) FIVR (Section 4.1). Both VR systems, as well as the data collection for the control condition, were run on an ASUS ROG Zephyrus Gaming PC Laptop, with an Intel i7-8750H at 3.9 GHz, 16GB DDR4 RAM and a GeForce GTX 1070. The Conventional/Control condition is described in the following subsection (Section

Fig. 6. illustrations of the Overhead Press exercise (left) and the Side Arm Raise exercise (right).

5.5.1), while the other two conditions used the system as described in Section 4 to perform the exercises. An overview of the followed procedure can be seen in Fig. 7.

5.5.1. Conventional/Control condition

The Control condition followed the process followed for physical exercise at the care institution. PwD performed physical exercises under the guidance of their physiotherapist, without receiving any other external stimuli or feedback. Movement information of the arms was again captured with the VIVE Trackers for analysis. Visual assistance to participants with performing the training task was provided if needed (see Fig. 8).

5.5.2. Protocol

In each session, the participant was invited to a familiar room at the ward along with their physiotherapist. They were asked to sit on a chair in the middle of the room and rest their arms to their sides. The therapist filled in the OERS questionnaire based on the emotional state of the PwD before coming to the session. The PwD were asked to select an emotion that represented their current state from VAS.

The required equipment (i.e., flat-screen TV, and interaction devices) were presented to participants, and information related to the way they will be used was provided. For the FIVR condition, information was also given about the HMD which was the most unfamiliar device. Participants were allowed to hold and observe the headset before putting it on and the experimenter addressed any questions they had. Finally, information related to the virtual content was offered to the participants for both the SIVR and FIVR conditions. During this time, their attention was directed to the virtual environment that was mirrored on the TV. For the FIVR condition, participants put on the HMD and experienced the virtual environment for a couple of minutes, during which they were asked

Fig. 8. Conventional/Control training where a visual assistant is provided to the PwD.

to describe what they were looking at. An open discussion session was held between the PwD and the researcher.

After the familiarization phase, and before the start of each exercise, participants performed a single repetition of the exercise. The movement trajectory of this repetition, including the starting and ending position of the tracked joints, were recorded and used as calibration for the subsequent exercise. This was done to ensure that the expected movement from the participants will be based on their own ROM. The repetition was repeated, as required, based on feedback from the therapist that a valid repetition was performed. This personalization of the experience

Fig. 7. The procedure followed during the experimental session. The three different conditions (control, FIVR, SIVR) are described in Sections 5.5.1 and 4 respectively. Details about all the questionnaires being administered can be found in Section 5.4.2.

for each exercise task, can help with avoiding any frustrations from participants, while also enabling them to successfully perform the exercise tasks based on their physical capabilities.

Once the calibration was completed successfully, the training began, with participants performing each exercise for 10 repetitions. For the SIVR and FIVR conditions, two targets, one for each arm, appeared in the virtual environment. The targets were placed at the starting (lower) position of the hand, as it was recorded during the calibration procedure. When touched by the participant, the targets disappeared from the starting position, and a new one appeared at the ending (higher) position, again based on the data from calibration. Once the user touched the targets at the ending position, these re-appeared at the starting position. The participant performed the exercise by moving their arms between the targets. In the Conventional/Control condition, patients performed the exercises without any visual feedback. At the end of all the repetitions, the therapist filled the OERS questionnaire and marked how many times they had to interfere and help the patient with performing the exercise.

The three conditions were counterbalanced, and after each condition, PwD were asked to select again an emotion from VAS based on how they felt. In the SIVR and FIVR conditions, they were also asked the questions from the simplified VRSQ, SUS, and SEQ questionnaires. A 3-minute break was then ensued before starting the next condition. Once all conditions were completed, participants answered a set of questions in a semi-structured interview format. The questions were open-ended to allow further discussion, and covered the emotional state of PwD, their understanding of the performed session, any memories that it might have triggered, as well as general feedback about the procedure. Overall, each experimental session lasted approximately 30 min.

5.6. Data analysis

To analyse the accuracy, task independence, time, and movement (see section 5.4.1), a Friedman test followed by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to examine the differences between the three types of training (FIVR, SIVR, and Conventional/Control) for the two exercise tasks (Overhead Press and Side Arm Raise). A Friedman test with post hoc analysis with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests was also used to compare the participants' emotions before, during, and after each training (FIVR, SIVR, and Conventional/Control) using the scores from the Observed Emotion Rating Scale (see section 5.4.2). Finally, paired-samples t-tests were conducted to compare participants' emotions measured by the Visual analogue Scale, before and after the three training sessions (see section 5.4.2) and to compare the sense of presence and usability between the SIVR and the FIVR experiences (see section 5.4.2). Data collected through the semi-structure interviews were analysed in (reference is hidden for blind review), and a summary of the results will be presented.

6. Results

6.1. Task-related metrics

Following are the results from the task-related metrics collected, as described in Section 5.4.1. In summary, these include the accuracy at

performing the required repetitions, the ability to perform the task independently, the time required to complete each exercise, the quality of movement during the exercise, and the focus of PwD based on eye tracking data.

6.1.1. Accuracy

A Friedman test was performed, followed by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, that found no significant differences in the task accuracy ratings amongst the three conditions (Table 1). However, even with no significant results, it was shown that participants in the FIVR performed the Overhead Press exercise more accurately compared to the SIVR and the Conventional/Control training. As already mentioned, the Overhead Press exercise was expected to be more difficult than the Side Arm Raise, indicating that FIVR systems may be more effective for more complicated exercises. On the other hand, for the Side Arm Raise, we found that participants performed the exercise more accurately during the SIVR and the Conventional/Control training. We believe that this result was affected by the visual feedback presentation. For the Overhead Press, the targets were presented into the front side of the demented person while for the Side Arm Raise the targets were presented to the sides of the person for the FIVR system as opposed to the SIVR.

6.1.2. Task independence

Related to the ability of PwD to perform the task on the own, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, showed significant differences amongst the three training sessions for both the Overhead Press ($\chi^2(2) = 14.00, p = .001$) and the Arm Raise ($\chi^2(2) = 19.11, p = .000$) exercises were found (Table 2). The results revealed that the physiotherapist assisted the PwD fewer times during the FIVR training compared to the SIVR and Conventional/Control type of training. Results also showed that the PwD were less independent during the Conventional/Control execution of the exercise compared to the SIVR training. Overall, these results, indicate that the use of technology can help the PwD perform the training exercises more independently.

6.1.3. Time

Analysis of the time required to complete each exercise, using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, revealed significant differences amongst the three training sessions for both the Overhead Press ($\chi^2(2) = 8.28, p = .016$) and Arm Raise Exercises ($\chi^2(2) = 12.34, p = .002$) (Table 3). Specifically, participants executed the easy Side Arm Raise exercise faster when using the FIVR version of the system compared to the SIVR and the Conventional/Control training. However, they completed the more complex Overhead Press exercise faster with the Conventional/Control training than with either the FIVR or the SIVR.

The analyses of time and accuracy suggested the presence of a speed-accuracy trade-off in the Overhead Press. Indeed, correlation analysis revealed that task accuracy and time performance were almost perfectly correlated in the FIVR condition ($r = 0.992, n = 5, p = .001$). That is, when the training was performed with the FIVR version of the system, participants took longer but executed the exercise more accurately.

6.1.4. Movement

Similarly, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, found significant differences in the movement quality scores amongst the three training sessions for

Table 1 Task accuracy (1 to 10 scale) for the selected exercises during the three training sessions.

Exercise	p		M	SD	Mdn	Phase	Z	p
Overhead Press	.717	Control	8.70	3.06	10.00	Control & SIVR	-0.74	.462
		SIVR	8.30	3.40	10.00	Control & FIVR	-1.16	.248
		FIVR	7.90	3.86	10.00	SIVR & FIVR	-0.82	.414
Arm Raise	.638	Control	8.70	3.05	9.00	Control & SIVR	-0.53	.595
		SIVR	8.75	3.13	10.00	Control & FIVR	-0.41	.684
		FIVR	8.00	4.10	10.00	SIVR & FIVR	-1.07	.285

Table 2
Task independence (1 to 10 scale) for the selected exercises during the three training sessions.

Exercise	p		M	SD	Mdn	Phase	z	p
Overhead Press	.001	Control	5.70	4.32	8.00	Control & SIVR	-1.57	.118
		SIVR	4.10	3.69	5.00	Control & FIVR	-3.30	.001
		FIVR	.95	1.15	1.00	SIVR & FIVR	-3.32	.001
Arm Raise	.000	Control	5.20	4.60	6.00	Control & SIVR	-0.567	.571
		SIVR	6.10	4.61	10.00	Control & FIVR	-3.10	.002
		FIVR	.75	1.33	.00	SIVR & FIVR	-3.35	.001

Table 3
Time (measured in seconds) for the selected exercises during the three training sessions.

Exercise	p		M	SD	Mdn	Phase	Z	p
Overhead Press	.016	Control	44.50	40.23	35.00	Control & SIVR	-2.42	.016
		SIVR	57.56	49.43	48.50	Control & FIVR	-0.77	.444
		FIVR	42.20	18.98	43.50	SIVR & FIVR	-1.35	.178
Arm Raise	.002	Control	53.75	31.52	52.00	Control & SIVR	-1.89	.059
		SIVR	39.05	21.09	35.00	Control & FIVR	-2.48	.013
		FIVR	39.60	28.42	42.50	SIVR & FIVR	-0.41	.679

both the Overhead Press ($\chi^2(2) = 20.65, p < .001$) and the Arm Raise Exercises ($\chi^2(2) = 18.67, p < .001$) (Table 4). Participants performed the exercises more accurately with the FIVR system compared to the SIVR and the Conventional/Control training. The movement quality was equal for the Conventional and the SIVR system.

6.1.5. Eye tracking

To evaluate the attentional focus of the PwD during task execution, gaze data were recorded and analysed from the built-in eye-tracker. Both exercises displayed similar results and are thus presented together. For the majority of the time during each exercise (almost 70% of the time), PwD were looking around in the virtual environment. During the rest of the time, their focus was split between three different areas: (1) the visual targets, (2) the mirrored avatar representing the PwD movement, and (3) the PwD's virtual hands, tracked by the Vive trackers. Regarding the total time they were looking at each of the three areas (dwell time), PwD spent most of the time looking at the mirrored avatar ($M = 63.5\%, SD = 30.2\%$). At the same time, they were more time fixated at a set point when they were looking at the targets ($M = 58.6\%, SD = 37.6\%$) (Fig. 9).

6.2. Questionnaire data

The emotional state of PwD during the sessions, and the overall usability of the system, as described in Section 5.4.2, were analysed and presented next.

6.2.1. Observed emotion rating scale (OERS)

OERS was used to assess the participants' emotions before, during, and after the training. Significant differences were reported only for the FIVR training. In particular, a Friedman test indicated that ratings of pleasure significantly differed before ($M = 2.20, SD = 2.01$), during ($M = 4.80, SD = 0.89$) and after ($M = 4.8, SD = 0.89$) VR exposure, $\chi^2(2) = 22.0, p = .000$. Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with a Bonferroni correction documented a significant increase in pleasure from before to during (Z

$= -3.32, p = .001$) and before to after ($Z = -3.32, p = .001$) the VR exposure but there was no significant difference in pleasure scores recorded between during and after the VR exposure ($Z = 0.00, p = 1.000$).

The Friedman test also indicated significant differences for the ratings of anxiety/fear before ($M = 3.30, SD = 2.05$), during ($M = 1.80, SD = 0.95$) and after ($M = 1.10, SD = 0.72$) VR exposure, $\chi^2(2) = 22.00, p = .000$. Post hoc analysis with a Bonferroni correction showed a significant decrease in anxiety/fear from before to during ($Z = -3.07, p = .002$) and from before to after the VR exposure ($Z = -3.32, p = .001$) and during and after the VR exposure ($Z = -3.07, p = .002$).

In addition, the Friedman test revealed significant differences for the ratings of sadness between before ($M = 3.20, SD = 2.07$), during ($M = 1.55, SD = 0.60$) and after ($M = 1.00, SD = 0.00$) the VR exposure, $\chi^2(2) = 22.00, p = .000$. Wilcoxon signed-rank tests indicated a significant decrease in sadness from before, during and after VR exposure ($Z = -3.32, p = .001$). Finally, there were no significant differences in the ratings of anger or general alertness before, during, and after the VR exposure. Both exercises yielded similar ratings $\chi^2(2) = 6.00, p = .051$ (Fig. 10).

Significant differences were reported only for the SIVR training only for the ratings of anxiety/fear. In particular, a Friedman test indicated significant differences for the ratings of anxiety/fear before ($M = 1.10, SD = 0.72$), during ($M = 1.90, SD = 1.55$) and after ($M = 1.90, SD = 1.55$) VR exposure, $\chi^2(2) = 14.00, p = .001$. Post hoc analysis with a Bonferroni correction showed a significant decrease in anxiety/fear from before to during and from before to after the exposure, with similar ratings ($Z = -2.42, p = .015$). No significant differences were detected during and after the exposure ($Z = 0.000, p = 1.000$).

Friedman test indicated that there were no significant differences between the SIVR condition in the ratings of pleasure $\chi^2(2) = 1.64, p = .44$, anger $\chi^2(2) = 1.64, p = .44$, anxiety $\chi^2(2) = 0.80, p = .67, p = .78$, sadness $\chi^2(2) = 0.29, p = .87$ or general alertness $\chi^2(2) = 3.71, p = .16$, before, during and after the conventional training.

Similarly, no significant differences in the ratings of pleasure $\chi^2(2) =$

Table 4
Movement quality (0 to 1 scale) for the selected exercises during the three training sessions.

Exercise	p		M	SD	Mdn	Phase	Z	P
Overhead Press	.000	Control	.68	.18	.69	Control & SIVR	-0.08	.071
		SIVR	.70	.23	.79	Control & FIVR	-0.18	.000
		FIVR	.80	.12	.89	SIVR & FIVR	-0.07	.016
Arm Raise	.000	Control	.68	.14	.74	Control & SIVR	.02	.914
		SIVR	.70	.13	.73	Control & FIVR	-0.10	.000
		FIVR	.82	.12	.87	SIVR & FIVR	-0.12	.000

Fig. 9. Percentage of fixation time (left) and dwell time (right) per area of interest, during the FIVR training session.

Fig. 10. Means and Standard Deviations of the observed ratings of emotions before, during and after the FIVR training.

1.13, $p = .57$, anger $\chi^2(2) = 0.40$, $p = .82$, anger $\chi^2(2) = 0.80$, $p = .67$, anxiety $\chi^2(2) = 1.80$, $p = .41$, sadness $\chi^2(2) = 2.53$, $p = .28$ or general alertness $\chi^2(2) = 1.33$, $p = .51$, before, during and after the conventional training. were present when comparing the ratings before, during and after the training session in the Conventional training session.

6.2.2. VAS

VAS provides a self-assessment by PwD related to their emotions towards the different sessions, and its analysis using paired-samples t-tests, and in line with the above findings, found a significant difference in the scores before ($M = 2.40$, $SD = 1.60$) and after ($M = 0.85$, $SD = 1.02$) the FIVR training $t(19) = 1.55$, $p = .000$. No significant difference was found between VAS scores before and after the SIVR training $t(19) = 0.35$, $p = .26$. Interestingly we observed significant difference in the scores before ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 2.13$) and after ($M = 3.35$, $SD = 2.25$) of Conventional/Control training $t(19) = -2.99$, $p = .008$. The findings are suggesting that PwD were happier after the FIVR training and sadder

after the Conventional/Control training (Fig. 11).

6.2.3. Presence and system usability

As expected, results indicated that presence was significantly higher in the FIVR ($M = 6.89$, $SD = 0.21$) than in the SIVR ($M = 2.11$, $SD = 2.21$) conditions ($t(18) = -4.78$, $p = .000$). No significant differences were shown between the FIVR ($M = 82.91$, $SD = 11.86$) and the SIVR ($M = 78.89$, $SD = 12.10$) VR versions of the system for usability. Note that the analysis is performed at 0 to 100 rates. To do so SUS required to subtract 1 from the user responses to positive statements and subtract corresponding values from 5 in the negative statements. All responses are added and multiply by 2.5. ($t(18) = -4.03$, $p = .06$).

6.2.4. Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews reflect upon whether VR is a feasible solution for PwD who are dealing with barriers arising from cognitive and motor impairments, such as, difficulties with orientation, attention,

Fig. 11. Means and Standard Deviations of the Visual Analogue Scale emotions before and after the VR exposure.

memory, language processing and lack of motivation. Using qualitative approaches, we found that VR could be a successful solution for physical activity in dementia patients when specific factors of the design are followed. Our findings suggested that VR appeared to be very effective for this clinical population if the design includes features that respond to specific challenges, such as: 1) a simple interaction modality is preferred for the PwD to be able to interact with the system and perform the task correctly and without much supervision and assistance from the clinical staff. Having that said body-trackers were found to enhance PwD concentration compared to the controllers; 2) visual targets should be stable, visible, and within the frontal field of view of the PwD so that the patients could interact easier and appropriately with the system. Also, continuous feedback should be provided to the PwD so as to be able to accurately perform the exercises with more precision; 3) personalised virtual environments relevant to the PwD's interests and memories improve the patient's mood, immersion and engagement, and 4) a reasonable range of deviation in which the patient will be allowed to perform the exercise is highly suggested since this can increase task performance.

7. Discussion

The COVID-19 pandemic stressed the healthcare systems at a worldwide level and placed vulnerable patients, like elderly people with dementia, at an increased risk of serious morbidity, because of their advanced age and frequent medical comorbidities (Cipriani and Di Fiorino, 2020; Brown et al., 2020). Consequently, PwD have been highly recommended to adhere to social distancing. As already mentioned, such measures may accelerate cognitive deterioration and amplify the behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia. In addition, the management of outpatient clinics with cancellation or postponement of outpatient visits stresses the healthcare systems further and increases the caregivers' burden and distress (Bonavita et al., 2020).

Experts in the field of dementia have made several recommendations about dementia care to patients and their caregivers, with recommendations to facilitate telemedicine and e-health assistive integrated solutions to replace traditional face-to-face visits for vulnerable patients, without hampering the quality of consultation (Cuffaro et al., 2020; Goodman-Casanova et al., 2020; Hatcher-Martin et al., 2020).

The use of assistive technology and especially VR technology to enhance the physical training of PwD is a relatively new approach, but one that can deliver routine health care and prevent the risk of viral

exposure, especially for PwD who are at higher risk. With this study, we aimed to evaluate the deployment of SIVR and FIVR systems into restricted health care units by comparing the effectiveness of the systems against the conventional routine training of PwD. Results showed that both types of VR interventions were very effective for our sample of 76 to 86-year-old older adults of both genders living with dementia. Our results also suggest that FIVR technology is more efficient in improving the accuracy in difficult exercises and completion time in easy exercises, as well as the level of independence compared to the SIVR and the conventional routine training. At the same time, the FIVR improved the emotional behaviour of PwD. Our results showed the FIVR induces a state of euphoria and pleasure, and reduced sadness, fear and anxiety.

Overall, our findings demonstrated that VR is a feasible and acceptable solution to support and enhance PwD physical training. Our finding that PwD can perform more accurately and more independently the training activities when assisted by FIVR than SIVR and the conventional routine training is in line with previous research suggesting that VR can enhance and support the PwD physical training (Eisapour et al., 2018a, b). However, extending past research (see systematic literature review by Schiza et al., 2019), our study, to the best of our knowledge, is the first to implement the technology in a hospital environment where people with dementia are confined during the pandemic period. We believe that VR as a technology is a feasible solution that can be integrated into practice to enhance the regular physical training of PwD. However, it is important to accept that the type of VR selected for each patient might differ based on each patient's needs. In contrast to SIVR, which is projected at flat-screen interfaces, FIVR systems envelop the users view completely. Because of the material factors of the system, this might cause anxiety or motion sickness to some PwD. As a result, FIVR systems may not be applicable to all patients. In such cases, SIVR can be administered to support the PwD's physical training. Similar findings were reported in previous studies as well, suggesting that VR might not be a solution for everyone (Matsangidou et al., 2020; Tabbaa et al., 2019).

Our study showed that when simple exercise tasks such as the Side Arm Raise, are executed by the PwD, the use of VR technology can reduce the required time of the training. PwD performed the exercise in less time and felt less exhaustion. For more complicated exercises such as the Overhead Press, PwD required more time to perform the exercise, but they executed it more accurately. The findings are in line with previous studies suggesting that VR can improve the outcomes of the training for healthy adults, by modulating the individual's willingness to

continue to exercise for a longer time, primarily by reducing the intensity of negative perceptions of pain and effort associated with exercise (Matsangidou et al., 2017; 2019). The above results were observed in both the SIVR and FIVR systems which shows that the use of interactive markers and a gamified experience can have beneficial effects on the performance of PwD during physical exercise.

Notably, the FIVR had a positive impact on PwD emotions. Specifically, significant improvements were observed during and after the VR exposure in pleasure, sadness, and fear/anxiety. It is worth mentioning that the observed improvements in the emotions of the PwD might be attributed to the high rates of usability and immersion. We, therefore, believe that new technologies have brought to life opportunities to provoke much more positive emotions in the PwD. Our findings are in line with those from previous studies showing that PwD can benefit from the use of VR if the system is appropriately designed (Eisapour et al., 2018a).

We also found that pleasurable and fun training can improve the patients' emotions, which resulted in an overall positive impact on PwD physical training. In particular, previous research suggested that even though the benefits of physical activity and exercise are well documented, most PwD are reluctant to engage in any form of physical activity because they find the physical training to be boring and tedious (Nyman, 2011; Suttanon et al., 2012). This reaction is to be expected given that dementia is linked to increased apathy, loss of motivation and interest in the self (Clarke et al., 2008; Crombie et al., 2004; Kitching, 2015; Muliya and Varghese, 2010). Our study showed that with a fun and engaging task, VR can serve as a useful intervention to improve the physical training of PwD, while at the same time eliciting positive emotions for the training. A previous study showed significant improvements in the PwD mood after being exposed to 360° videos of their preference (Rose et al., 2020). To our knowledge, this is the first study to report significant improvements in PwD mood after using a FIVR and interactive VR system.

Regarding presence, our results revealed that PwD are able to experience presence that is significantly higher when exposed to a FIVR system compared to the SIVR version. This was not only validated by the self-reported questionnaires, but also from the observations made through eye-tracking. Based on the collected eye-tracking data, the PwD while being exposed to VR, spent a significant amount of time looking at their virtual hands. This suggests that embodiment was high since they were able to relate to their virtual hands as if they were real. Similarly, to previous studies with healthy individuals, hand ownership is a significant component of presence and immersion (Matsangidou et al., 2017, 2019). The findings also showed that PwD felt more confident when using the FIVR system compared to the SIVR system. Based on a previous study, it seems that the sense of presence can be elevated by incorporating personalised features relevant to each patients' background (i.e., a scenery close to the village they were born) and interests and using simple and light equipment (i.e., use body-trackers instead of controllers) (Matsangidou et al., 2020). Finally, FIVR allowed limiting distractions as it enveloped the users' vision and restricted it to the virtual world. This may have allowed the older participants to better focus their attention on the task-relevant items, compared to the SIVR and the Conventional training methods.

Incorporating eye-tracking to the study not only allowed us to understand more properly the sense of presence PwD were having, but also suggested that PwD need constant feedback. As dementia progresses, cognitive functions such as attention, memory, and language comprehension, decline and interfere with the understanding of the exercises (Savva et al., 2009; Yu, F., & Kolanowski, 2009). Having the visual targets within the front field of view of PwD, along with the mirrored avatar of the movement, can provide constant feedback to the PwD and as a result to be able to perform the exercise more accurate and without the need for human assistance.

We would also like to draw the reader's attention to the deployment challenges of VR in health care units. In contrast to deploying VR in

other settings, we need to recognize the difficulties PwD have with physical movement as well as the hospital's space restrictions. Choosing a technology that is portable and easy to set up in hospital environments is essential. Similar challenges and solutions were also suggested by a previous study with PwD (Tabbaa et al., 2019). During our study, the equipment was set up in a room of a confined mental health unit for PwD. A speedy and easy setup of the equipment was a crucial factor to avoid PwD experiencing any sort of discomfort. It is worth mentioning, that this was even more important once the patient was entering the room since PwD behaviour challenges are very common (Beck et al., 2008), with physical and verbal aggression toward self or others being a usual behaviour (Cohen-Mansfield, 2001). Therefore, to reduce the risk of upsetting the patient the equipment was offered as soon as possible, but with a clear explanation. This was also an important part of the deployment process since PwD are dealing with high levels of anxiety (Seignourel et al., 2008). High anxiety rates are usually resulting in an unwillingness to try unknown technologies (Phelan et al., 2021) which was the case for VR. Our patients were exposed for the first time to VR and therefore, the unfamiliarity of this technology made the patients sceptical. To overcome this issue, we provided all patients with time for familiarization where VR was demonstrated to them. Familiarizing themselves with the equipment made the patients less anxious and more willing to try the technology. In our study, we used the HTC Vive HMD, which is connected to a PC via a wire. To ensure that the PwD were comfortable, and the wire would not affect the patient or interrupt negatively the training, we used a shelf to place the PC far from the patient, keeping at the same time the wire behind. An alternative solution would have been to use a wireless standalone VR system (e.g., Oculus Quest), which will decrease space restriction.

The results of this study provide evidence that FIVR technology can play a significant role in the improvement of PwD physical training and emotional health. In particular, our findings revealed positive effects of VR on the PwD who could, using our system, experience the outside world while exercising in a safe and restricted hospital environment. Overall, our results suggest that FIVR can increase positive emotions (e.g., pleasure and happiness), decrease negative emotions (e.g., sadness and fear/anxiety), and improve the performance and independence of the PwD when performing a gamified exercise (e.g., boost the patients training by targets and reinforcement). This results in PwD having an increased willingness to engage in the task, which is a key factor for the success of any training regime.

8. Limitations and future work

A limitation of the current study is the administration of some of the questionnaires (VRSQ, SUS, and SEQ), that have not been previously validated for use with PwD. The questionnaires were adjusted when communicating them to the PwD, to make them easier to understand. A further validation study should still be performed to ensure their validity with the population. Related to the use of the eye-tracking technology, and because of the lack of ability from PwD to follow exact instructions regarding the technology, the eye-tracker was not calibrated per participant, and some of the data could contain additional noise. Instances where too much noise with the data was observed, were removed from the analysis.

Since one of the goals of the paper was to assess the feasibility and acceptability of the system, we did not measure any long-term physical effects using the VR system, as well as the possibility of unsupervised VR training. This will be part of our future work, in a program that we have already started, performing a longitudinal study with the population. The study will also be able to measure additional long-term effects on the cognitive level of PwD as a result of the physical training.

Future work should consider ways to reduce exclusion criteria, for example, PwD confined to bed could be addressed by setting up the equipment into their private rooms.

Authors contributions

Maria Matsangidou: Conception or design of the work, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, drafting of the article, provided HCI guidelines for system's design and development.

Fotos Frangoudes: System design and development, data collection, data analysis, drafting of the article.

Marios Hadjjaros: System development.

Eirini Schiza and Kleanthis C. Neokleous, Marios Avraamides and Constantinos S. Pattichis: Review of the article.

Ersi Papayianni: Patients' screening.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

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